

Freezing of a Supercooled Water Drop after an Impact onto a Solid Wall

Mingyue Ding, Jeanette Hussong, Ilia V. Roisman *

Institute for Fluid Mechanics and Aerodynamics, Technical University of Darmstadt, Peter-Grünberg-Straße 10, Darmstadt 64287, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Impact freezing
Supercooled water drop
Nucleation
Airflow
Roughness

ABSTRACT

Supercooled water freezes as a result of ice nucleation, propagation along the substrate of a thin ice layer and subsequent expansion of a mushy region of ice dendrites. In this experimental study, the impact, spreading and solidification of the drop are observed in a cold wind tunnel using a high-speed video system. The statistics of the nucleation times after a supercooled water drop impacts onto a dry solid substrate are analyzed. The experiments demonstrate that the rate of the ice nucleation is enhanced significantly by drop impact and continuously reduces over time. The nucleation rate increases with higher impact velocity and is enhanced by the substrate roughness. This effect is explained by the presence of the small bubbles in the liquid drops, generated by drop impact and fast spreading. The surfaces of these bubbles serve as the additional triggers for ice nucleation. Moreover, the effect of the presence of the bubbles becomes even more significant when the wetted area reduces due to the drop receding. The average number of the nucleation sites in this case increases, since the number of bubbles does not reduce despite the reductions of the wetted area. These bubbles are probably captured by the receding contact line.

1. Introduction

In the face of contemporary climate adversities, the phenomenon of ice formation emerges not merely as a natural occurrence but rather as a potent peril. Under cold conditions, ice formation and accretion engender formidable hazards spanning diverse sectors, encompassing aircraft (Gent et al., 2000; Mishchenko et al., 2010), transmission lines (Wang, 2017), power production (Fakorede et al., 2016; Lamraoui et al., 2013) and other application fields (Sojoudi et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2019). In many scenarios, ice formation ensues following the impact of supercooled droplets on working surfaces, leading to their subsequent freezing.

There are several phases of solidification of a supercooled drop in contact with a surface. The onset of a first-order phase transition is referred to as nucleation. Once ice embryos form and grow until they reach a critical size (Libbrecht, 2017) to overcome the Gibbs free energy barrier, releasing latent heat as the solid-liquid interface forms. This marks the initial irreversible formation of a stable nucleus. Notably, nucleation can occur in two distinct modes: homogeneous nucleation, prevalent at exceedingly low temperatures below approximately -40°C , and heterogeneous nucleation, where the nucleus forms on the surfaces of the substrate, interfaces with the surrounding gas, or adheres to solid particles and bubbles. Because of the inherently stochastic

nature of molecular motion, nucleation itself is a stochastic process. Some studies have explored factors influencing the nucleation process, such as the degree of supercooling (Sun et al., 2019; Schremb et al., 2017b), electric fields (Zhou et al., 2024) and suspended particles (Okawa et al., 2001; Hallett, 1964).

Following heterogeneous nucleation at the surface of a solid substrate, a thin layer of ice is formed which expands along the substrate surface. The spreading of this ice layer has been observed in Thiévenaz et al. (2019); Kong and Liu (2015); Schremb et al. (2017a). Thiévenaz et al. (2020) found that the formation of an ice layer beneath the liquid film limits the maximum spreading of the drop compared to isothermal conditions, and this reduction in spread is particularly pronounced for colder surfaces. For water supercooled to $\Delta T \approx 7.0\text{ K}$, the ice layer expands at a constant propagation speed, depending on both the liquid temperature and the thermal properties of the wall. Subsequently, at sufficiently low liquid temperatures, the surface of the initial ice layer becomes unstable at certain points. This instability leads to the rapid kinetic crystal growth of single dendrite or a front of numerous dendrites into the bulk liquid, resulting in an opaque liquid–solid mushy layer (Jaafar et al., 2017; Lambley et al., 2023). Additionally, the velocities of ice crystal dendrites have been investigated (Rodrigues et al., 2011; Schremb et al., 2018). It has been shown that the crystal growth rate is directly influenced by the contact temperature rather than the initial

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: roisman@sla.tu-darmstadt.de (I.V. Roisman).

temperature of the substrate (Koldewej et al., 2021). Furthermore, Grivet et al. (2022) found that the velocity of ice crystals matches the contact line velocity when the droplet stops.

After the dendritic freezing phase, the liquid-solid mixture reaches a local thermodynamic equilibrium. If the surface remains cold, the liquid between the mushy layers will continue to solidify. However, this process progresses much more slowly and has been referred to as secondary solidification (Jung et al., 2012) or planar freezing (Schreimb et al., 2018).

Various studies have been carried out on the solidification of supercooled droplets, such as freezing of sessile drops (Zhang et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2022; Alizadeh et al., 2012), the effect of wettability on the surfaces (Boinovich et al., 2014; Fuller et al., 2024) or the influence of drop impact on solidification statistics (Schreimb et al., 2017b; Zhang et al., 2018). Comprehensive reviews are recommended for a better understanding of the basic phenomena accompanying water solidification (Libbrecht, 2017) and the interaction of the icing processes with the liquid flow associated with the wetting of solid surfaces (Roisman and Tropea, 2021). Nevertheless, during the process of supercooled drops solidification, such as when it impacts an aircraft wing, only a small amount of the drops freezes immediately upon impact, leaving the rest of the still-liquid supercooled drops to be carried along the surface by the surrounding airflow. This can lead to ice buildup occurring far behind the leading edge of the aircraft (Bureau, 1965). The research regarding the solidification of supercooled drop impact at different impact velocities, especially considering the influence of airflow, is still not well understood.

Therefore, in this study, the impact of a single supercooled drop on substrates with varying roughness has been experimentally investigated by a high-speed optical system. The processes of supercooled drops impacting onto substrates with varying roughness under different wind speeds are recorded. Both hydrodynamics and statistics regarding the freezing process were studied and analyzed. By elucidating the influence of airflow and surface roughness on the freezing process of the supercooled drops impact, this study may shed light on the implications for aviation safety and engineering, offering pathways for the development of effective strategies to mitigate ice accretion and its associated risks.

2. Experimental method

The experiments involving high-speed observations of the impact of a supercooled drop and its solidification on substrates were carried out in a wind tunnel placed in a cold chamber.

2.1. Experimental setup

The setup, shown schematically in Fig. 1, comprises five main

Fig. 1. Icing wind tunnel setup for investigating the impact of supercooled drops.

elements: a cold chamber, a drop generator, a wind tunnel, a test section, and a high-speed video system.

The cold chamber, equipped with a cooling unit, can reach temperatures as low as -20°C , with its heat exchanger mounted on the ceiling. To ensure effective cooling of the chamber and compensate for the heat generated by other measurement equipment, the unit delivers a minimum cooling power of 2500 W across all temperature ranges. The cold chamber controls the temperature of the air, drops, and substrates to ensure they are all at the same temperature. In this study, we controlled the temperature at -10°C .

The drop generator is suspended in a shroud pipe above the wind tunnel, which serves to protect it. To produce supercooled drops, purified de-ionized water (Millipore, Milli-Q®) is utilized, dripping from a syringe needle positioned at the same height as a water tank, which is located outside the chamber. The syringe diameter determines the drop volume, and this method ensures that drops with reproducible sizes can be created (Tropea et al., 2007). The size of the drop in this study is $D_0 = 2.6 \pm 0.1$ mm. A thermocouple is threaded through the syringe needle and near the outlet of the syringe to measure the temperature of the supercooled drop. Upon release from the syringe, the drop undergoes acceleration due solely to gravity until it reaches the end of the shroud pipe. Subsequently, the drop experiences further acceleration from the airflow before impacting the substrate in the test section.

A vertical, open-return wind tunnel allows for the variation of airflow velocity directed parallel to the drop's motion. The air enters the wind tunnel through an inlet nozzle and passes into a settling chamber. Within the settling chamber, a honeycomb structure with cells measuring 4 mm in diameter and 24 mm in length is used to eliminate large-scale vortices. This is followed by a fine mesh screen composed of 0.3 mm wires arranged in a 1.3 mm grid pattern, designed according to the specifications outlined by Barlow et al. (1999). Both flow straighteners have a central 8 mm hole to allow the injection shroud pipe to pass through. This design effectively removes any large-scale vortices and ensures that the airflow is uniform. The flow then moves on to a nozzle before reaching the test section, where droplets alter the impact velocity. After leaving the test section, the flow is decelerated and further expanded by another diffuser before reaching the fan. A circular flexible duct is used to prevent the transmission of any vibrations to the fan. The majority of the wind tunnel ducts and diffuser are made of acrylic glass, which ensures visibility of the impact in the test section and allows us to check for any deposited water or ice inside other parts of the wind tunnel. Moreover, during the experiments, the humidity in the cold chamber is kept below saturation to prevent the formation of large ice crystals that could affect the experiments. The airflow velocity can be provided in the range from 0 to 40 m/s with a turbulence intensity of 0.5%. In this study, the maximum airflow velocity is limited to 20 m/s which corresponds to the highest temporal resolution of the high-speed video system to ensure that all moments of drop impact can be captured by the high-speed camera.

In the test section, various aluminum substrates with different roughness levels are used to investigate the processes of the impact and solidification of a supercooled drop. The substrate is mounted in a target holder which is covered by a 3D-printed shell with rounded edges to prevent detachment of the flow at sharp edges. The impact and solidification processes are tested and recorded in the test section with the help of an optical system.

A high-speed optical system is placed in the cold chamber to record the impact and solidification processes. A light source positioned on one side of the test section provides sufficient illumination, and a high-speed camera (Photron SA-X2 k1080), situated on the opposite side, is tilted to capture a top-down view for the observation. Due to variations in substrate reflectivity, the experimental recording rate achieves 10,000 frames per second (fps) for polished substrates and 8000 fps for rough surfaces. A spatial resolution of $52.91 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ is used to capture the impact process and accurately determine the onset of freezing.

Due to the recording time constraints of the high-speed camera, the

video recording time for polished substrates is within a duration of 17.473 s, while for rough surfaces, it extends to 21.842 s. Accounting for the reaction time required to trigger recording, the freezing delay time post-impact for polished substrates is limited to approximately 15 s, and it is approximately 18 s for rough surfaces. Hence, the nucleation and solidification results after impact presented below have been limited to approximately 15 s for polished substrates, and 18 s for rough substrates.

2.2. Experimental materials

Three different aluminum substrates are used in the experiments: polished substrate, rough surface R3 (sandblasted at 3-bar pressure), and rough surface R6 (sandblasted at 6-bar pressure). Standard parameters, characterizing the substrate morphology obtained through 3D optical profilometry - Confocal microscope (*Sensofar, S Neox*) on three substrates, are shown in Table 1. A magnification lens 50 \times has been used in the optical setup of the profilometer.

One example of the morphology of a rough substrate is shown in Fig. 2. It can be observed that the surfaces consist of a mesh of interconnected ridges and grooves with random shapes. For rough surface R6, the top height of the ridges, like the depth of the grooves, is approximately 5–7 μm .

The wetting properties of the substrates are listed in Table 1. The values of the static advancing and receding contact angles, θ_{adv} and θ_{rec} , have been determined using a standard shadowgraphy observation of a slow spreading of a sessile drop formed at the substrate by a fixed syringe. The data for the receding contact angle of rough surfaces is missing since any attempt to force dewetting leads to the loss of the stability of the contact line, yielding an emergence of cusps and fingers.

The physical properties of supercooled water at the temperature -10°C are listed in Table 2. The impact parameters, air velocity U_{air} , drop impact velocity U_0 , Weber, Reynolds and aerodynamic Weber [determined in (6)] numbers, We , Re , We_{air} and the residual (minimum) thickness of the lamella h_{res} , respectively, are listed in Table 3. To avoid experimental contingency, especially for the nucleation process, the experiment was repeated at least 20 times at each state point and for each substrate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydrodynamics and wetting

Representative impact processes of a supercooled drop onto a cold polished substrate at various impact velocities are shown in Fig. 3. These are the typical outcomes of drop impact onto a solid substrate (Josserand and Thoroddsen, 2016; Yarin et al., 2017). The observed phenomena include drop deformation in a decelerating gas flow near the substrate (Gloerfeld et al., 2021), drop deformation during the initial stage of wall collision, and the generation of a thin radially expanding lamella bounded by a Taylor rim (Taylor, 1959; Roisman et al., 2002). Additionally, the levitation of the lamella, caused by its interaction with the surrounding gas (Driscoll et al., 2010; Schroll et al., 2010; Riboux and Gordillo, 2014), leads to the emergence of a corona. This is followed by a

Table 1

Parameters characterizing the morphology and wetting properties of the three substrates used in the experiments: Sa is the arithmetic mean height, Sq is the root mean squared height, Sz is the maximum height. θ_{adv} and θ_{rec} are the static advancing and receding contact angles.

	Polished Al	R3	R6
Sa (nm)	4.46 \pm 0.16	748.82 \pm 0.04	1118.93 \pm 0.09
Sq (nm)	5.81 \pm 0.29	960.56 \pm 0.05	1456.40 \pm 0.11
Sz (nm)	42.35 \pm 6.02	5677.76 \pm 0.40	8889.42 \pm 0.93
wetting properties			
θ_{adv}	93.64 \pm 3.06 $^\circ$	121.49 \pm 3.36 $^\circ$	118.90 \pm 3.90 $^\circ$
θ_{rec}	46.06 \pm 1.23 $^\circ$	–	–

Fig. 2. An example of the morphology of a surface element of the rough surface R6, obtained using the 3D optical profilometry.

Table 2

Physical properties of supercooled water at the temperature -10°C .

Density ρ	Surface tension σ	Viscosity μ
998.2 kg/m 3 (Hare and Sorensen, 1987)	77.3 mN/m (Roland, 1985)	2.66 mPa-s (Hallett, 1963)

Table 3

List of impact parameters. The theoretical predictions from (Roisman, 2009) for the residual (minimum) thickness of the lamella h_{res} are calculated using (4).

	U_{air} (m/s)	U_0 (m/s)	We	Re	We_{air}	h_{res} (μm)
n. 1	0	4.1	560	3980	0	75
n. 2	10	4.8	765	4650	4.2	70
n. 3	15	5.3	950	5190	9.4	67
n. 4	20	6.5	1430	6370	16.7	62

splash resulting from the rim instability and the instability of the corona (Burzynski et al., 2020), ultimately forming secondary drops. At later stages of drop spreading on the substrate, the evolution of the spreading diameter is determined by the dynamics of the rim. If the substrate is partially wettable (as in our case of the polished substrate), the capillary forces govern the receding of the rim. The phenomenon of the spreading of a liquid drop of supercooled water is the same as of any other Newtonian drop.

During drop spreading, several bubbles with diameters ranging from 50 to 100 μm can be identified forming at the region of the advancing contact line, as shown in the fourth image in Fig. 3a. These bubbles are more pronounced as they accumulate in the rim region during retraction (see the bottom row in Fig. 3). We cannot observe smaller bubbles since these sizes are at the limit of the optical system used in the experiments. The bubbles are collected in the rim region since they are formed due to clearly visible instabilities of the propagating contact line. On the other hand, the larger bubbles are transported by the liquid flow in the lamella, which moves faster than the rim (Taylor, 1959; Roisman et al., 2002). The dislodging of the bubbles in the lamella is governed by the balance of the force F_{lam} , applied by the flow in the lamella and by the capillary force F_σ associated with the substrate wettability. The flow in the lamella is a function of radius and time (Yarin and Weiss, 1995), but it is on the order of the drop impact velocity U_0 . The Reynolds number around a bubble of diameter 50 μm is $Re_{\text{bubble}} \sim 100$. Therefore, the inertia is important even for such small length scales as the bubbles. The shape of the bubble at the substrate can be approximated as half of a sphere with a diameter D_{bubble} . Therefore, the hydrodynamic force can be estimated in the form

$$F_{\text{lam}} \approx \frac{\pi}{16} \rho U_0^2 C_d D_{\text{bubble}}^2 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. Dynamics of impact of a drop of diameter $D_0 = 2.6 \pm 0.1$ mm onto the polished substrate at various airflow velocities. The images correspond to the various dimensionless times defined as $\hat{t} = tU_0/D_0$: drop shape just before impact at $\hat{t} = -0.16$, lamella formation at $\hat{t} = 0.3$, corona splash at $\hat{t} = 0.8$, pizza-like shape of the spreading lamella, bounded by a rim at $\hat{t} = 4$, drop receding at $\hat{t} = 14$. The drop impact velocities in case a) and b) are 4.1 and 6.5 m/s, respectively. The width of the view of each image is 13 mm.

where the drag coefficient $C_d \approx 0.6 - 0.8$, which is estimated using CFD computations (Ade, 2019) of the flow past a sessile drop for various Reynolds numbers and contact angles.

The capillary force from the substrate applied on a sessile bubble is

$$F_\sigma \approx \sigma D_{\text{bubble}} (\cos\theta_{\text{rec}} - \cos\theta_{\text{adv}}) \quad (2)$$

The smallest diameter of a bubble D_{bubble}^* , which is transported by the lamella to the rim is estimated from the balance of these two forces, defined in (1) and (2). The condition $F_{\text{lam}} = F_\sigma$ yields

$$D_{\text{bubble}}^* \approx \frac{16\sigma(\cos\theta_{\text{rec}} - \cos\theta_{\text{adv}})}{\pi\rho U_0^2 C_d} \quad (3)$$

For the impact velocity $U_0 = 4.1$ m/s, the estimation yields $D_{\text{bubble}}^* \approx 20$ μm . This estimation is confirmed by the observations of larger bubbles collected in the rim region. This conclusion is important for the interpretation of the freezing phenomena because the ice nucleation can be influenced by the presence of nano-bubbles on the substrate surface (Schremb et al., 2017b).

3.1.1. Lamella rupture

The process of bubble entrapment during fast liquid spreading becomes more intensive on rough substrates, which introduces additional disturbances to the advancing contact line. The influence of the substrate morphology is probably even more significant for the specific shapes used in these experiments, such as those shown in Fig. 2. One can identify the formation of an array of dints, formed as a result of the sandblasting process. The dints are bounded by a continuous network of ridges and grooves. The air can be trapped by the dints, which can even introduce some effective slip effect to the flow in the lamella. Several examples of a supercooled water drop impacts onto the rough surface R3 and R6 are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. It can be seen that the surface complex morphology significantly disturbs the spreading contact line, despite the fact that the characteristic height of the roughness ($\sim 10^1 \mu\text{m}$) is much smaller than the typical lamella thickness ($\sim 10^2 \mu\text{m}$) at these impact parameters. The values of the residual lamella thickness, given in Table 3, estimated using the validated theoretical predictions (Roisman, 2009)

$$h_{\text{res}} = 0.79D_0 Re^{-2/5} \quad (4)$$

The disturbances result in the appearance of fingering instability (Marmanis and Thoroddsen, 1996; Aziz and Chandra, 2000; Mehdizadeh et al., 2004), leading to the formation of the dry radial channels in the lamella during the early stages of spreading $\hat{t} \equiv tU_0/D_0 < 1$. Such channels have been observed after drop impact onto a substrate with radial patterns of wettability, formed by alternating hydrophilic and hydrophobic sectors (Lee et al., 2010).

For impact onto rough surfaces with the morphology shown in Fig. 2, the channels are formed as a result of dynamic interactions between the spreading lamella and the elements of the surface. This process is similar to the crater formation as a result of body entrance (Bergmann et al., 2009; Truscott et al., 2014). At higher impact velocities, $U_0 = 6.5$ m/s, accompanied by the 20 m/s airflow, the width of the channels, estimated from the images of drop spreading, is 100–200 μm . This width is comparable to the characteristic size of the dints (see Fig. 2) and with the residual thickness of the lamella (the theoretical predictions for h_{res} are given in the Table 3). At the final stages of drop impact, the open channels form an array of dry holes in the lamella, as seen in Fig. 4b and Fig. 5b.

The formation of such holes after drop impact onto a rough surface has been observed previously (Dhiman and Chandra, 2010). The criterion for hole formation on the wall films is usually described considering the energy balance of the surfaces emerging due to the hole formation (Sharma and Ruckenstein, 1990). However, it seems that the formation of the holes after an impact onto a rough substrate is not a static but dynamic process. They formed due to the pinned contact lines of the dry channels in the lamella. In any case, the rupture of the lamella is observed if the bubble size is of the same order as the lamella thickness. The outcomes of the impact of a supercooled drop onto the rough substrates are shown in Fig. 6. The holes are promoted by the surface roughness and impact velocity. No holes have been observed on the polished substrate since the diameters of the bubbles resided in the spreading lamella are much smaller than the residual film thickness.

3.1.2. Maximum drop spreading

Numerous models for the maximum spreading diameter can be found in the literature (Josserand and Thoroddsen, 2016). In this study, the validated model from Roisman (2009) is applied

Fig. 4. Dynamics of impact, splash, spreading and receding onto the rough surface R3 of a drop of diameter $D_0 = 2.6 \pm 0.1$ mm at various airflow velocities. The images correspond to the various dimensionless times: $\hat{t} = 0.59, 1.0, 2.2, 3.8$ and 7.5 . The drop impact velocities in cases a) and b) are 4.1 and 6.5 m/s, respectively. The width of the view of each image is 13 mm.

$$\hat{D}_{\max} \equiv \frac{D_{\max}}{D_0} = 0.87Re^{1/5} \left(1 - \frac{0.46Re^{1/5}}{We^{1/2}} \right) \quad (5)$$

which is valid only for cases when the effect of the airflow is negligibly small.

This correlation is based on the characteristic lamella thickness, defined in (4) and is valid for the impact velocities not exceeding the splashing threshold. The term including the Weber number is estimated from the relative Taylor rim velocity. This relative rim velocity can be influenced by the presence of the airflow. The upper bound for the maximum spreading, associated with zero rim relative velocity, therefore can be estimated from the mass balance $\hat{D}_{\mu} \sim Re^{1/5}$. The evolution of the spreading diameter is determined by the dynamics of the rim. The relative Taylor rim velocity can be estimated in the form $U_{\text{rim}} \sim \sqrt{(\sigma - F_{\text{air}})/\rho h}$, where the aerodynamic force per rim length is estimated in the form $F_{\text{air}} \sim \rho_{\text{air}} U_{\text{air}}^2 h_{\text{rim}}/2$. Here ρ_{air} is the air density,

Fig. 5. Dynamics of impact, splash, spreading and receding onto the rough surface R6 of a drop of diameter $D_0 = 2.6 \pm 0.1$ mm at various airflow velocities. The images correspond to the various dimensionless times: $\hat{t} = 0.25, 0.8, 1.5, 3.0$ and 6.5 . The drop impact velocities in cases a) and b) are 4.1 and 6.5 m/s, respectively. The width of the view of each image is 13 mm.

$\rho_{\text{air}} U_{\text{air}}^2/2$ is the aerodynamic pressure at the center of the substrate and h_{rim} is the rim height. To estimate the importance of the aerodynamic forces, we introduce the dimensionless property $\varepsilon \equiv F_{\text{air}}/\sigma$ which can be expressed in the form

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\hat{h}_{\text{rim}} We_{\text{air}}}{2}, \quad We_{\text{air}} \equiv \frac{\rho_{\text{air}} U_{\text{air}}^2 D_0}{\sigma} \quad (6)$$

The duration t_{\max} of the drop spreading can be estimated by the instant when the thickness of the viscous boundary layer $\sim \sqrt{\nu t}$ is equal to the thickness of the lamella $\sim D_0/(tU_0/D_0)^2$, as estimated from the mass and momentum balance in [Yarin and Weiss \(1995\)](#). In [Roisman \(2009\)](#) this instant is estimated in the form

$$\hat{t}_{\mu} \approx 0.6Re^{1/5} \quad (7)$$

As can be seen in [Fig. 7](#), the values for \hat{t}_{\max} are rather close to the

Fig. 6. Images of the lamella at long times after drop impact onto the rough surfaces R3 and R6 at -10°C and various impact velocities.

Fig. 7. Dimensionless time \hat{t}_{\max} corresponding to the drop maximum spreading as a function of the impact velocity U_0 . The impact parameters are listed in Table 3.

theoretical predictions for t_{μ} . It is interesting that \hat{t}_{\max} monotonically decreases with increasing substrate porosity. This effect can be explained by the disturbances of the flow in the lamella generated by the

elements of the substrate morphology. These perturbations appear as the three-dimensional capillary waves at the lamella surface, which can be seen in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Now, the volume of the rim at the point of maximum spreading can be estimated as $V_{\text{rim}} \sim \pi D_{\max} U_{\text{rim}} h_{\text{res}} t_{\mu}$. On the other hand, the volume of the rim can be estimated by approximating the rim cross-section with a half circle of radius h_{rim} . This leads $V_{\text{rim}} \sim \pi D_{\max} \pi h_{\text{rim}}^2 / 2$. The volume balance yields the equation for the rim size in the form

$$\hat{h}_{\text{rim}}^2 = \frac{0.24 \sqrt{2 - \hat{h}_{\text{rim}} We_{\text{air}}}}{We_{\text{air}}^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

which can be rewritten with the help of expression (6)

$$\varepsilon^2 = \frac{0.085 We_{\text{air}}^2 \sqrt{1 - \varepsilon}}{\sqrt{We}} \quad (9)$$

Finally, the expression (5) for the maximum spreading diameter can be modified to account for the aerodynamic effects by replacing σ by $\sigma - F_{\text{air}}$. This yields

$$\hat{D}_{\max} \approx 0.87 Re^{1/5} \left(1 - \frac{0.46 Re^{1/5}}{We^{1/2}} \sqrt{1 - \varepsilon} \right) \quad (10)$$

where ε is a real positive root of Eq. (9).

The comparison of the maximum spreading diameter with the theoretical predictions (5) for the case $U_{\text{air}} = 0 \text{ m/s}$, and (10) is shown in Fig. 8. The airflow leads to some minor increase in the maximum spreading diameter but does not lead to any qualitative changes. One additional effect of the airflow is the initial drop deformation prior to impact (Gloerfeld et al., 2021), which is not taken into account in the present considerations. In any case, the existing knowledge of the hydrodynamics of spreading can be applied also to the impact of super-cooled drops as long as they remain liquid.

3.2. Freezing: nucleation and solidification

3.2.1. Observations of freezing

Variations in substrate roughness and airflow velocities significantly influence the freezing process and ultimately shape the final ice formation. Selected examples of the phenomena associated with drop freezing are shown in Fig. 9. The red arrow indicates the nucleation site, while the dashed red line represents the initial freezing advancing front, with the yellow arrow indicating the direction of movement. In many cases, as in Fig. 9a, the nucleation site, marked by the red arrow, can be identified once the liquid ceases to move. It is known that solidification is initiated at some instant by heterogeneous ice nucleation, mainly at the substrate surface, followed by an expansion of a thin ice layer along

Fig. 8. Dimensionless maximum spreading diameter \hat{D}_{\max} at various impact velocities U_0 in comparison with the theoretical predictions. The impact parameters are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 9. Images of the mechanisms of drop freezing during the receding stage after impact onto different substrates at -10°C . (See supplementary videos for more details.)

the substrate (Kong and Liu, 2015; Schremb and Tropea, 2016; Kong and Liu, 2018). The instabilities in the growth of this ice layer lead after some time to the emergence of a cloud of dendrites. In Fig. 9 the emergence of dendrites is shown in the middle image for each of the three selected impact cases. The solidification appears as an expanding area shaded with thin dark lines. The dendritic cloud forms a mushy layer of the temperature close to the melting point. The secondary stage of solidification of the liquid water in the mushy layer is much slower than the speed of the dendrite propagation, as illustrated in Fig. 10. This can be observed by the lighter color of the liquid water compared to the darker frozen ice.

The final shape of the splat is determined not only by the impact parameters but also by the time of drop freezing. In our experiments, drop freezing has never been observed during the spreading phase, as

this time frame is too short for dendrite formation. Often, freezing occurs during the rim receding stage, which is considerably longer on wettable surfaces compared to the spreading stage. The typical pizza-like shapes obtained after the drop freezing during the rim receding stage are shown in Fig. 9. These special shapes consist of the frozen drop lamella bounded by a rim. Moreover, the holes produced by impact onto rough substrates also remain after freezing, as shown in Fig. 9c.

It is noteworthy that not every drop freezes during the receding process, resulting in a pizza-like shape. For an extended period of freezing on the polished substrate, the drop fully recedes into a sessile drop. Then, after a few seconds, the drop freezes, as depicted in Fig. 11. Alternatively, in certain cases, the drop may retain its liquid state within the 15 s recording period of the high-speed camera.

The cases shown in Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b are rather interesting. For

Fig. 10. Images of the secondary solidification after drop impact onto the rough surface R6 at -10°C . The drop impact velocity is 4.8 m/s.

Fig. 11. Selected snapshots capturing the mechanisms of drop freezing after complete receding after impact onto the polished substrate at -10°C . The drop impact velocity is 4.8 m/s.

some reason, the mushy layer apparently does not penetrate the central lamella region of the drop. Let us first consider the freezing of a thin ice layer before the emergence of the dendrites. Since the thermal effusivity of the aluminum surface is very high, approximately $\varepsilon_{\text{wall}} = 23000 \text{ J/m}^2\text{Ks}^{1/2}$ (Blaine, 2018), heat conduction dominates the freezing process through the solid substrate, the ice layer, and the liquid water region. The temperature and heat flux are continuous at the wall/ice boundary. The temperature of the water and the ice are equal to the melting point at the ice/water interface. The rate of ice growth is determined by the Stefan conditions. The well-known similarity solution for this problem (Alexiades and Solomon, 1992) yields the thickness of the ice layer

$$h_{\text{ice}} = 2s\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{ice}}t} \quad (11)$$

where α is the thermal diffusivity and the parameter s is the root of the equation

$$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}s}{St} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{wall}}\exp(-s^2)}{\varepsilon_{\text{wall}}\text{erf}(s) + \varepsilon_{\text{ice}}} + \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{liq}}\exp(-\nu^2s^2)}{\varepsilon_{\text{ice}}(1 - \text{erf}[\nu s])}, \quad (12)$$

$$\nu = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{\text{ice}}}{\alpha_{\text{liq}}}}, \quad St = \frac{(T_{\text{melt}} - T)c_{\text{ice}}}{L} \quad (13)$$

where St is the Stefan number, $\varepsilon_{\text{wall}}$, ε_{liq} and ε_{ice} are the thermal effusivities of the substrates, liquid and ice, L is the latent heat of fusion, while α_{ice} and α_{liq} are the thermal diffusivity of ice and liquid. Here, the minor effects associated with the different densities of the liquid water and ice are neglected. For known thermal properties of aluminum, ice and liquid water and the temperature $T = -10^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($\alpha_{\text{ice}} = 1.02 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $\alpha_{\text{liq}} = 1.2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $\varepsilon_{\text{ice}} = 2200 \text{ J/m}^2\text{Ks}^{1/2}$, $\varepsilon_{\text{liq}} = 1600 \text{ J/m}^2\text{Ks}^{1/2}$, $\varepsilon_{\text{wall}} = 23000 \text{ J/m}^2\text{Ks}^{1/2}$, and $c_{\text{ice}} = 2108 \text{ J/kgK}$), the solution of (12) yields $s = 0.16$.

The dendrites appear at some short time, t_{dendr} , after the inception of the thin ice layer. This time for the temperature $T = -10^{\circ}\text{C}$, estimated from the supplementary video N3 to Schreimb and Tropea (2016), is $t_{\text{dendr}} \sim 5 \text{ ms}$. The ice layer thickness at this instant, estimated from (11), is $h_{\text{ice}} = 23 \mu\text{m}$. Moreover, the thickness of the thermal boundary in liquid water region is $h_{\text{thermal}} \approx 2\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{liq}}t_{\text{dendr}}}$, which is approximately $50 \mu\text{m}$. In our experiments, the value $h_{\text{thermal}} + h_{\text{ice}}$ is of the same order as the residual thickness h_{res} of the lamella (see Table 3). Therefore, if the nucleation occurs before the complete receding of the drop, the relatively warm region near the thin ice layer (of the temperature close to T_{melt}) on the substrate expands over the lamella before the formation of the dendrites. At times $t > t_{\text{dendr}}$ the similarity solution is no longer valid and the heat transfer in the lamella is dominated by the boundary conditions at the free surface of the lamella. The final pizza-like shape of the drop is obtained by fast solidification of the lamella surrounded by the rim.

3.2.2. Time delay for drop freezing

Denote by N_0 the total number of drop impact tests with the same impact parameters and operating conditions. Denote t_i as the freezing

time of the i -th drop in the experimental series, with $i \leq N_0$. The i -th drop remains liquid for times $t < t_i$. For this experimental set, the number of liquid drops N_{liq} reduces with time t due to their solidification.

The heterogeneous nucleation of a supercooled liquid on a cold substrate is governed by the nucleation rate $J(t)$ which depends on the substrate and liquid materials, substrate morphology and temperature. The average number of the nucleation sites n on the area $A_c(t)$ wetted by the drop during the spreading ($t < t_{\text{max}}$) and receding ($t > t_{\text{max}}$) phases can be estimated in the form

$$n = \begin{cases} \int_0^t A_c(\tau)J(\tau)d\tau, & t < t_{\text{max}} \\ \int_0^{t_A} A_c(\tau)J(\tau)d\tau + A_c(t) \int_{t_A}^t J(\tau)d\tau, & t > t_{\text{max}} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

here τ is a dummy variable and t_A is the instant at which the diameter reaches the value of $A_c(t)$ during the spreading phase. This expression accounts for the hypothesis that the ice nuclei formed during spreading can disappear in the receding phase if they are located outside the wetted region. These expressions can be simplified for long times after spreading

$$n \approx A_c(t)\lambda(t), \quad \lambda \equiv \int_0^t J(\tau)d\tau, \quad t \gg t_{\text{max}} \quad (15)$$

where $\lambda(t)$ is the number of the nucleation sites per unit area of the wetted spot. A drop remains liquid at the instant t if the number of the nucleation sites on the wetted area A_c is zero. The probability p_{liq} of this state can be estimated from the Poisson's distribution (Feller, 1968)

$$p_{\text{liq}} = \exp[-n] \quad (16)$$

The probability $p_{\text{liq}}(t) \approx N_{\text{liq}}(t)/N_0$ can be estimated experimentally when the number $N_{\text{liq}}(t)$ which solidifies at times exceeding t is known. The average number of the nucleation sites per unit area, $\lambda(t)$, and the average nucleation rate, $J(t)$, can now be estimated using (15) and the experimental data for the statistics of the freezing times

$$\lambda(t) \approx \frac{1}{A_c(t)} \ln \left[\frac{N_0}{N_{\text{liq}}(t)} \right], \quad J(t) = \frac{d\lambda}{dt} \quad (17)$$

valid for times $t \gg t_{\text{max}}$.

For a constant value of the wetted area, for example for static sessile drops, and for a constant value of the nucleation rate J , the evolution of the number of liquid drops should follow the relation $\ln(N_0/N_{\text{liq}}) \sim t$. This is not the case for nucleation of a liquid drop after a wall impact. One example of the evolution of N_{liq} is shown in Fig. 12. The nucleation frequency is much higher during the short times after impact, $t < 1 \text{ s}$, and reduces at the longer times $t > 1 \text{ s}$. The evolution of $\ln[N_0/N_{\text{liq}}(t)]$ allows us to calculate the main statistical properties of the nucleation statistics: the average number of the nucleation sites per unit area λ , the characteristics distance between the sites $\delta \equiv 1/\sqrt{\pi\lambda}$, and the nucleation rate J . These values are shown in Fig. 13 for the polished substrate. It can

Fig. 12. Evolution of the ratio N_{liq}/N_0 for drops impacting onto the polished substrate at various impact velocities.

(a) Nucleation sites per unit area

(b) Distance between sites, $\delta \equiv 1/\sqrt{\pi\lambda}$

(c) Nucleation rate $J \equiv d\lambda/dt$

Fig. 13. Statistical parameters of nucleation on polished substrate at various impact velocities: (a) average number of nucleation sites per unit area, calculated using Eq. (17), (b) characteristic distance between the nucleation sites and (c) nucleation rate J , calculated using Eq. (17).

be found that higher impact velocities are associated with increased nucleation rates, a phenomenon that becomes more pronounced on rough substrates, as illustrated in Fig. 14.

The surprising result is that the average number of nucleation sites, λ , exhibits a dependence on the impact velocity at times significantly longer than the duration of drop spreading, which is approximately 5

(a) Nucleation sites per unit area

(b) Nucleation rate $J \equiv d\lambda/dt$

Fig. 14. Statistical parameters of nucleation on rough surface R6 at various impact velocities: (a) average number of nucleation sites per unit area, calculated using Eq. (17) and (b) nucleation rate J , calculated using Eq. (17).

ms. Which mechanism allows the system to “remember” about drop impact seconds after the collision?

One scaling relation of the value of λ and for the nucleation rate J , which can be found in Koldewej et al. (2021), gives a significant insight into the understanding of the physics of nucleation. However, this theory can not help us to explain the significant increase of the nucleation rate in the initial stages of impact and its dependence on the impact velocity. Therefore, some additional physical effects have to be taken into consideration.

In Schremb et al. (2017b) we have assumed that the duration of the initial stage of intensive nucleation is determined by the typical time t_{bubble} of dissolving of the bubbles, created by drop collision. This hypothesis is supported by the observations of the significantly lower nucleation rate for supercooled water degassed prior to the impact experiments. This can be explained by the reduction of the time dissolving in the degassed water. Significant enhancement of the ice nucleation by the presence of the gas bubbles has been observed by the numerous experiments (Ohsaka and Trinh, 1998; Zhang et al., 2003; Hu et al., 2013) demonstrating ultrasonic-induced ice nucleation. The nucleation enhancement has been observed also after the laser-induced cavitation (Knott et al., 2011) or by the presence of a stationary bubble (Heneghan and Haymet, 2003). The physical processes involved in the ice nucleation initiated by a collapse of an inertial gas bubble governed by acoustic cavitation, are modeled in Cogné et al. (2016a, 2016b).

The duration of dissolving (Epstein and Plesset, 1950) of an air bubble of the radius R_{bubble} can be estimated as $t_{bubble} \sim R_{bubble}^2 \rho_{air} / 3D_{air} c_{air}$, where $\rho_{air} = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $D_{air} \approx 6.7 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ are the density and the diffusion coefficient of air (Wilke and Chang, 1955), c_{air} is the air solubility. The solubility of air in the supercooled water at -10°C is around 4% by volume (Langham and Mason, 1958) that yields $c_{air} = 4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg/m}^3$. The estimated radius of an air bubble in the lamella is $R_{bubble} = D_{bubble}^* / 2 \approx 10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The typical time of the bubble dissolving is therefore $t_{bubble} \approx 1 \text{ s}$. This value is of the same order as the observation time in our experiments.

These estimations allow us to assume the mechanism of bubble-assisted ice nucleation in a drop, while the bubbles are created due to drop impact and fast spreading on a solid substrate. Higher impact ve-

locity leads to more intensive bubble generation, which explains the increase of the ice nucleation rate for higher impact velocity. The ice nucleation rate reduces over time since the number of bubbles reduces due to their dissolution in water. While it has been observed that on rough substrates, at lower impact velocities ($U_0 = 4.1$ m/s and $U_0 = 4.8$ m/s), the nucleation rate initially decreases. However, towards the end of the process, there is a subsequent increase (see Fig. 14). Compared with the polished substrate, rough substrates tend to enhance the stability and quantity of air bubbles, resulting in a slower dissolution process. On the other hand, the internal convection induced by low velocity impacts is relatively weak, leading to a slower dissolution rate. Consequently, the slower dissolution may contribute to the higher nucleation rate observed at longer durations on rough substrates.

One can expect that since the bubble formation is enhanced on rough substrates (see Fig. 2), the ice nucleation will also be intensified on such substrates. The comparison of the parameter λ for various substrates is shown in Fig. 15. At short times after impact, the values of λ indeed increase with the substrate roughness. However, at larger times, the number λ for polished substrate increases and even exceeds the corresponding values for rough surface R3. This fact can be explained by the significant drop receding on the polished substrate (see Fig. 11) in comparison with the contact line pinning on the rough surfaces (see Fig. 10). Correspondingly, the wetted area on the polished substrate is much smaller. The increase of the nucleation rate on the smaller area can be explained that the bubbles are captured by the receding contact line. The existing bubbles do not necessarily disappear during drop receding. This is why the number per unit area may grow as a result of the drop receding.

4. Conclusions

An experimental investigation in a cold wind tunnel was conducted to examine the impact of a supercooled water drop onto substrates with varying degrees of roughness at different wind speeds. The results revealed notable differences in drop behavior and nucleation rates across different substrates and drop impact velocities.

Drop impact and spreading lead to the generation of air bubbles on the substrates. These bubbles act as effective nucleation sites, resulting in a higher nucleation rate with increased impact velocity due to greater bubble production. Additionally, the morphology of rough substrates, characterized by ridges and grooves, intensifies bubble entrapment. Consequently, substrates with greater roughness exhibit higher nucleation rates.

However, bubbles dissolve in water. The dissolution time for 20 μm bubbles is approximately 1 s. This dissolution process explains the continuous reduction in nucleation rate over time.

It is interesting that on the polished substrate, partially wettable substrates, bubbles do not disappear during receding but are driven by the contact line. These bubbles remain and continue to serve as sources for ice nucleation.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2024.104359>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mingyue Ding: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jeanette Hussong:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Iliia V. Roisman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT, DeepL, and Grammarly to polish the English language. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take

Fig. 15. Effect of the surface roughness on the average number of the nucleation sites λ . The drop impact velocity is 6.5 m/s.

full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data is available on Zenodo and is publicly accessible at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12600058.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956703 (SURFACE Smart surface design for efficient ice protection and control). The authors would also like to acknowledge the Research Foundation–Flanders (FWO Medium-scale infrastructure project I009220N) and KU Leuven internal funds (Medium-scale infrastructure project AKUL/17/026). Special thanks are extended to the Laboratory of Complex Surfaces and Interfaces (COMPLEXURF) at KU Leuven for their support in conducting the roughness measurements.

References

- Ade, M., 2019. Development of a Numerical Methodology for Water Management Simulations of Passenger Cars. Phd thesis. Technische Universität Darmstadt, Darmstadt.
- Alexiades, V., Solomon, A., 1992. Mathematical Modeling of Melting and Freezing Processes, 1st ed. Taylor & Francis, Washington, D.C.
- Alizadeh, A., Yamada, M., Li, R., Shang, W., Otta, S., Zhong, S., Ge, L., Dhinojwala, A., Conway, K.R., Bahadur, V., Vinciguerra, A.J., Stephens, B., Blohm, M.L., 2012. Dynamics of ice nucleation on water repellent surfaces. *Langmuir* 28, 3180–3186.
- Aziz, S.D., Chandra, S., 2000. Impact, recoil and splashing of molten metal droplets. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 43, 2841–2857.
- Barlow, J.B., Rae, W.H., Pope, A., 1999. *Low-Speed Wind Tunnel Testing*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bergmann, R., Van Der Meer, D., Gekle, S., Van Der Bos, A., Lohse, D., 2009. Controlled impact of a disk on a water surface: cavity dynamics. *J. Fluid Mech.* 633, 381–409.
- Blaine, R.L., 2018. In search of thermal effusivity reference materials. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 132, 1419–1422.
- Boinovich, L., Emelyanenko, A.M., Korolev, V.V., Pashinin, A.S., 2014. Effect of wettability on sessile drop freezing: when superhydrophobicity stimulates an extreme freezing delay. *Langmuir* 30, 1659–1668.
- Bureau, U.S.W., 1965. *Aviation Weather, for Pilots and Flight Operations Personnel*. US Government Printing Office.
- Burzynski, D.A., Roisman, I.V., Bansmer, S.E., 2020. On the splashing of high-speed drops impacting a dry surface. *J. Fluid Mech.* 892, A2.
- Cogné, C., Labouret, S., Peczański, R., Louisnard, O., Baillon, F., Espitalier, F., 2016a. Theoretical model of ice nucleation induced by acoustic cavitation. Part I: pressure and temperature profiles around a single bubble. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 29, 447–454.

- Cogné, C., Labouret, S., Peczkalski, R., Louisnard, O., Baillon, F., Espitalier, F., 2016b. Theoretical model of ice nucleation induced by inertial acoustic cavitation. Part 2: number of ice nuclei generated by a single bubble. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 28, 185–191.
- Dhiman, R., Chandra, S., 2010. Rupture of thin films formed during droplet impact. *Proc. R. Soc. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 466, 1229–1245.
- Driscoll, M.M., Stevens, C.S., Nagel, S.R., 2010. Thin film formation during splashing of viscous liquids. *Phys. Rev. E* 82, 036302.
- Epstein, P.S., Plesset, M.S., 1950. On the stability of gas bubbles in liquid-gas solutions. *J. Chem. Phys.* 18, 1505–1509.
- Fakorede, O., Feger, Z., Ibrahim, H., Ilinca, A., Perron, J., Masson, C., 2016. Ice protection systems for wind turbines in cold climate: characteristics, comparisons and analysis. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 65, 662–675.
- Feller, W., 1968. *An Introduction to Probability Theory and its Applications*, 3rd ed Vol. I. Wiley, New York.
- Fuller, A., Kant, K., Pitchumani, R., 2024. Analysis of freezing of a sessile water droplet on surfaces over a range of wettability. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 653, 960–970.
- Gent, R.W., Dart, N.P., Cansdale, J.T., 2000. Aircraft icing. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. London, Ser. A* 358, 2873–2911.
- Gloerfeld, M., Roisman, I.V., Hussong, J., Tropea, C., 2021. Measurements and modelling of the residual mass upon impact of supercooled liquid drops. *Exp. Fluids* 62, 1–11.
- Grivet, R., Monier, A., Huerre, A., Josserand, C., Séon, T., 2022. Contact line catch up by growing ice crystals. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 128, 254501.
- Hallett, J., 1963. The temperature dependence of the viscosity of supercooled water. *Proc. Phys. Soc.* 82, 1046.
- Hallett, J., 1964. Experimental studies of the crystallization of supercooled water. *J. Atmos. Sci.* 21, 671–682.
- Hare, D.E., Sorensen, C.M., 1987. The density of supercooled water. II. Bulk samples cooled to the homogeneous nucleation limit. *J. Chem. Phys.* 87, 4840–4845.
- Heneghan, A., Haymet, A., 2003. Liquid-to-crystal heterogeneous nucleation: bubble accelerated nucleation of pure supercooled water. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 368, 177–182.
- Hu, F., Sun, D.W., Gao, W., Zhang, Z., Zeng, X., Han, Z., 2013. Effects of pre-existing bubbles on ice nucleation and crystallization during ultrasound-assisted freezing of water and sucrose solution. *Innovative Food Sci. Emerg. Technol.* 20, 161–166.
- Jaafar, M.A., Rousse, D.R., Gibout, S., Bédécarrats, J.P., 2017. A review of dendritic growth during solidification: mathematical modeling and numerical simulations. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 74, 1064–1079.
- Josserand, C., Thoroddsen, S.T., 2016. Drop impact on a solid surface. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* 48, 365–391.
- Jung, S., Tiwari, M.K., Doan, N.V., Poulikakos, D., 2012. Mechanism of supercooled droplet freezing on surfaces. *Nat. Commun.* 3, 615.
- Knott, B.C., LaRue, J.L., Wodtke, A.M., Doherty, M.F., Peters, B., 2011. Communication: bubbles, crystals, and laser-induced nucleation. *J. Chem. Phys.* 134.
- Koldewij, R.B., Kant, P., Harth, K., de Ruijter, R., Gelderblom, H., Snoeijer, J.H., Lohse, D., van Limbeek, M.A., 2021. Initial solidification dynamics of spreading droplets. *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 6, L121601.
- Kong, W., Liu, H., 2015. A theory on the icing evolution of supercooled water near solid substrate. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 91, 1217–1236.
- Kong, W., Liu, H., 2018. Unified icing theory based on phase transition of supercooled water on a substrate. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 123, 896–910.
- Lambley, H., Graeber, G., Vogt, R., Gaugler, L.C., Baumann, E., Schutzius, T.M., Poulikakos, D., 2023. Freezing-induced wetting transitions on superhydrophobic surfaces. *Nat. Phys.* 19, 649–655.
- Lamraoui, F., Fortin, G., Benoit, R., Perron, J., Masson, C., 2013. Atmospheric icing severity: quantification and mapping. *Atmos. Res.* 128, 57–75.
- Langham, E., Mason, B.J.N., 1958. The heterogeneous and homogeneous nucleation of supercooled water. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. A Math. Phys. Sci.* 247, 493–504.
- Lee, M., Chang, Y.S., Kim, H.Y., 2010. Drop impact on microwetting patterned surfaces. *Phys. Fluids* 22.
- Libbrecht, K.G., 2017. Physical dynamics of ice crystal growth. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 47, 271–295.
- Liu, X., Chen, H., Zhao, Z., Yan, Y., Zhang, D., 2019. Slippery liquid-infused porous electric heating coating for anti-icing and de-icing applications. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 374, 889–896.
- Lu, M., Song, M., Pang, X., Dang, C., Zhang, L., 2022. Modeling study on sessile water droplet during freezing with the consideration of gravity, supercooling, and volume expansion effects. *Int. J. Multiphase Flow* 147, 103909.
- Marmaris, H., Thoroddsen, S., 1996. Scaling of the fingering pattern of an impacting drop. *Phys. Fluids* 8, 1344–1346.
- Mehdizadeh, N.Z., Chandra, S., Mostaghimi, J., 2004. Formation of fingers around the edges of a drop hitting a metal plate with high velocity. *J. Fluid Mech.* 510, 353–373.
- Mishchenko, L., Hatton, B., Bahadur, V., Taylor, J.A., Krupenkin, T., Aizenberg, J., 2010. Design of ice-free nanostructured surfaces based on repulsion of impacting water droplets. *ACS Nano* 4, 7699–7707.
- Ohsaka, K., Trinh, E.H., 1998. Dynamic nucleation of ice induced by a single stable cavitation bubble. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 73, 129–131.
- Okawa, S., Saito, A., Minami, R., 2001. The solidification phenomenon of the supercooled water containing solid particles. *Int. J. Refrig.* 24, 108–117.
- Riboux, G., Gordillo, J.M., 2014. Experiments of drops impacting a smooth solid surface: a model of the critical impact speed for drop splashing. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 113, 024507.
- Rodrigues, M.A., Miller, M.A., Glass, M.A., Singh, S.K., Johnston, K.P., 2011. Effect of freezing rate and dendritic ice formation on concentration profiles of proteins frozen in cylindrical vessels. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 100, 1316–1329.
- Roisman, I.V., 2009. Inertia dominated drop collisions. II. An analytical solution of the Navier–Stokes equations for a spreading viscous film. *Phys. Fluids* 21.
- Roisman, I.V., Tropea, C., 2021. Wetting and icing of surfaces. *Curr. Opin. Colloid Interface Sci.* 53, 101400.
- Roisman, I.V., Rioboo, R., Tropea, C., 2002. Normal impact of a liquid drop on a dry surface: model for spreading and receding. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 458, 1411–1430.
- Roland, A., 1985. *Model Research: the National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics, 1915–1958. Volume 1 of the NASA history Series. Scientific and Technical Information Branch, NASA, Washington, DC.*
- Schreimb, M., Tropea, C., 2016. Solidification of supercooled water in the vicinity of a solid wall. *Phys. Rev. E* 94, 052804.
- Schreimb, M., Campbell, J.M., Christensen, H.K., Tropea, C., 2017a. Ice layer spreading along a solid substrate during solidification of supercooled water: experiments and modeling. *Langmuir* 33, 4870–4877.
- Schreimb, M., Roisman, I.V., Tropea, C., 2017b. Transient effects in ice nucleation of a water drop impacting onto a cold substrate. *Phys. Rev. E* 95, 022805.
- Schreimb, M., Roisman, I.V., Tropea, C., 2018. Normal impact of supercooled water drops onto a smooth ice surface: experiments and modelling. *J. Fluid Mech.* 835, 1087–1107.
- Schroll, R.D., Josserand, C., Zaleski, S., Zhang, W.W., 2010. Impact of a viscous liquid drop. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 104, 034504.
- Sharma, A., Ruckenstein, E., 1990. Energetic criteria for the breakup of liquid films on nonwetting solid surfaces. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 137, 433–445.
- Sojoudi, H., Wang, M., Boscher, N., McKinley, G.H., Gleason, K.K., 2016. Durable and scalable icephobic surfaces: similarities and distinctions from superhydrophobic surfaces. *Soft Matter* 12, 1938–1963.
- Sun, M., Kong, W., Wang, F., Liu, H., 2019. Impact freezing modes of supercooled droplets determined by both nucleation and icing evolution. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 142, 118431.
- Taylor, G.I., 1959. The dynamics of thin sheets of fluid ii. Waves on fluid sheets. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. A Math. Phys. Sci.* 253, 296–312.
- Thiévenaz, V., Séon, T., Josserand, C., 2019. Solidification dynamics of an impacted drop. *J. Fluid Mech.* 874, 756–773.
- Thiévenaz, V., Séon, T., Josserand, C., 2020. Freezing-damped impact of a water drop. *Europhys. Lett.* 132, 24002.
- Tropea, C., Yarin, A.L., Foss, J.F., et al., 2007. *Springer Handbook of Experimental Fluid Mechanics, Vol. 1.* Springer.
- Truscott, T.T., Epps, B.P., Belden, J., 2014. Water entry of projectiles. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* 46, 355–378.
- Wang, Z., 2017. Recent progress on ultrasonic de-icing technique used for wind power generation, high-voltage transmission line and aircraft. *Energ. Build.* 140, 42–49.
- Wilke, C., Chang, P., 1955. Correlation of diffusion coefficients in dilute solutions. *AICHE J.* 1, 264–270.
- Yarin, A.L., Weiss, D.A., 1995. Impact of drops on solid surfaces: self-similar capillary waves, and splashing as a new type of kinematic discontinuity. *J. Fluid Mech.* 283, 141–173.
- Yarin, A.L., Roisman, I.V., Tropea, C., 2017. *Collision Phenomena in Liquids and Solids.* Cambridge University Press.
- Zhang, X., Inada, T., Tezuka, A., 2003. Ultrasonic-induced nucleation of ice in water containing air bubbles. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 10, 71–76.
- Zhang, X., Wu, X., Min, J., Liu, X., 2017. Modelling of sessile water droplet shape evolution during freezing with consideration of supercooling effect. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 125, 644–651.
- Zhang, R., Hao, P., Zhang, X., He, F., 2018. Supercooled water droplet impact on superhydrophobic surfaces with various roughness and temperature. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 122, 395–402.
- Zhou, X., Wang, H., Zhu, X., Chen, R., Liao, Q., 2024. Numerical study of supercooled water droplet impacting on cold superhydrophobic surface under electric field. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 218, 124781.